

AI and Teamwork in Agile Software Development: A Systematic Mapping Study

Kwok Ya Ting Crystal^[0009-0002-7818-0526] and Mahum Adil^[0000-0001-6452-6085]

Free University of Bozen-Bolzano, Italy,
yatingcrystal.kwok, mahum.adil@student.unibz.it

Abstract. *Background.* Agile software development relies on effective teamwork to achieve successful project outcomes. While the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into Agile practices has gained attention, its specific role in supporting teamwork remains relatively underexplored. *Aim.* This study provides a systematic overview of current research on AI in Agile teamwork, focusing on the 3Cs of teamwork: communication, collaboration, and coordination. *Method.* We conducted a Systematic Mapping Study (SMS) analyzing research studies published from January 2001 to January 2025. *Result.* Among the limited body of research focusing on teamwork, the studies are well distributed across the 3C aspects. Natural language processing (NLP) is the most widely studied AI technology, while large language models (LLM) remain underexplored. Furthermore, relatively few studies investigate higher-autonomy AI roles, such as agents and assistants. *Conclusion.* This study highlights key research gaps and suggests future opportunities to leverage advanced AI technologies to enhance teamwork in Agile software development.

Keywords: Agile Software Development · Artificial Intelligence · Teamwork · Communication · Collaboration · Coordination.

1 Introduction

Agile software development has transformed how software is built, enabling teams to adapt to change, enhance collaboration, and deliver software products iteratively [1]. Across industries, organizations have adopted Agile frameworks such as Scrum, Kanban, and Extreme Programming (XP) to improve flexibility, responsiveness, and team efficiency [2]. One of the core values of Agile, as outlined in the Agile Manifesto [3], is that individuals and interactions are valued over processes and tools. This, therefore, establishes teamwork — how teams collaborate, communicate, and coordinate — as a crucial part of Agile practices [4].

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has advanced significantly, revolutionizing various domains, including Agile software development [5]. AI applications extend beyond automation to support tasks such as bug detection, predictive analytics, and AI-powered assistants or chatbots that streamline workflows [6]. AI-driven techniques like machine learning (ML) and natural language processing (NLP)

are increasingly integrated into Agile software development to enhance productivity and efficiency [7].

2 Related Work

In recent years, research on AI in Agile software development has increased, with most studies focusing on improving workflows, processes and tools [6–8]. However, the exploration into AI in teamwork, one of the core aspect of Agile software development, remains unclear, as far as the authors are aware of.

On the other hand, research on teamwork in Agile software development has been well-established. Strode et al. [9] proposed the Agile Teamwork Effectiveness Model (ATEM) to identify key factors contributing to teamwork effectiveness while Hoda et al. [1] examined the evolution of Agile software development, tracing its historical development, adoption, and transformation across industries. While these studies provide valuable insights into teamwork, they do not investigate the use of AI in teamwork in Agile software development.

This research gap highlights the need to examine AI’s role in teamwork in Agile software development, referred to as Agile teamwork in this study. Building on existing systematic mapping studies, this study provides an overview of AI’s role in Agile teamwork, specifically in relation to 3C within Agile teams.

To address this gap, we systematically explore how AI technologies, roles and functions support each aspect of 3Cs in Agile teamwork [10]. The 3Cs are *communication - involving the exchange of information among team members; collaboration - focusing on joint problem-solving and shared decision-making; and coordination - ensuring the effective management of interdependent tasks.*

3 Research Methodology

This section presents the research methodology, based on the guidelines outlined by Petersen et al. [11], for conducting a systematic mapping study.

3.1 Research Questions

The primary objective of this SMS is to provide a comprehensive overview of research conducted on AI in the context of teamwork within Agile software development. To achieve this, the study is guided by the main research question: *What is the research conducted on Artificial Intelligence in Agile teamwork?*

To further refine the scope, we define key research questions (RQs) as follows:

- RQ1.** *What is the temporal distribution of studies?* Understanding the distribution of studies to identify patterns and trends over time.
- RQ2.** *What are the key characteristics of the studies?* Examining the dissemination of research across venues, analyzing the nature of the studies, and categorizing the research methods to identify different approaches.

- RQ3.** *What aspects of Agile teamwork are investigated in these studies?* Classifying studies within the 3C model for structured analysis of research.
- RQ4.** *What AI technologies and roles are explored in the studies?* Investigating the roles and functions that AI technologies played in Agile teamwork.

3.2 Search Protocol

The search process followed a systematic approach using a search string formulated based on the PICO (Population, Intervention, Comparison, and Outcomes) framework [11]. The search string was iteratively refined to incorporate synonyms and variations to provide comprehensive coverage of relevant terminologies used by practitioners and researchers [12, 13]. We used the following comprehensive query string to retrieve studies:

(“agile” OR “extreme programming” OR “xp” OR “kanban” OR “lean” OR
 “scrum” OR “crystal” OR “dsdm” OR “fdd” OR (“feature” AND “driven” AND
 “development”) OR “pair programming” OR “pp” OR “pair-programming”)
 AND (“software” OR “development” OR “software engineering”)
 AND (“artificial intelligence” OR “AI” OR “large language model” OR “LLM”
 OR “machine learning” OR “ML” OR “ChatGPT” OR “deep learning” OR
 “natural language processing” OR “NLP”)
 AND (“team” OR “teams” OR “teamwork”)

3.3 Screening of Papers

Figure 1 provides an overview of screening process, illustrating the number of papers retrieved, screened, and excluded at each stage. The search was conducted in three digital libraries, retrieving 462 papers (ACM: 28, IEEE Xplore: 85, Scopus: 349). These libraries were selected for their comprehensive coverage of studies in computer science and software engineering. IEEE Xplore and ACM Digital Library were selected due to their significant role in publishing high-quality research in the field. Additionally, Scopus was included to ensure a diverse range of sources and broaden the scope of our search.

Fig. 1: Number of included studies during screening of papers.

Table 1 presents the inclusion and exclusion criteria used in this study. We selected the timeframe (Jan 2001 - Jan 2025) for data extraction, as 2001 marks

the formal introduction of Agile software development. Since then, Agile methods have continuously evolved, shaping software development. Given the increasing integration of AI into Agile practices in recent years, this timeframe enables a comprehensive analysis of the research area of AI in relation to Agile teamwork over time. To minimize potential bias, the second author independently and randomly selected the papers for initial inclusion. Any uncertainties or disagreements were resolved through discussion and consensus. As a result, 20 studies were selected for detailed analysis.

Table 1: Inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Screening	ID	Criteria
Inclusion	IC1	Published between January 2001 and January 2025 inclusive
	IC2	Only English
	IC3	Published in conference, journal or magazine
	IC4	Studies with primary focus on Agile teamwork and AI for Agile
Exclusion	EC1	Published in workshop report, book, SLR, and SMS
	EC2	Duplicate papers
	EC3	No access to full text
	EC4	Studies not related to Agile Software Development
	EC5	Studies not related to Agile teamwork
	EC6	Studies focused on AI research (Agile for AI)
	EC7	Studies without AI

3.4 Keywording

In the next phase, we analyzed the abstracts and full texts of the selected papers to answer the research questions. A data extraction sheet was created to systematically collect relevant information from the studies. The collected data, including summarized results, can be accessed through the online repository¹.

4 Results

Answer to RQ1. Figure 2a shows the distribution of the 20 papers from 2018 to 2025. Notably, the papers from 2025 include only those published in January. Despite the inclusion criteria spanning from 2001, no papers were found prior to 2018, suggesting that research in this area has become prevalent in recent years.

Answer to RQ2. Figure 2a also shows that the majority of the selected studies are conference papers, with only three journal articles published from 2024 onwards. This indicates that research in this area is still in its early stages. To further classify the empirical studies, we adhered to the empirical standards of software engineering [14]. Figure 2b shows the empirical studies, which include

¹ 10.5281/zenodo.15543234

Fig. 2: Distribution of publication trends and research methodologies.

engineering research, experiments, action research, and data science methodologies. Among these, engineering research—focused on the proposal, development, and evaluation of technological artifacts—emerged as the most prevalent methodology. Most studies categorized as engineering research used experimental methods, case studies, or quantitative simulations to evaluate technological solutions.

Answer to RQ3. Figure 3 shows the distribution of studies across the 3C aspects of teamwork: collaboration, communication and coordination. Eight studies focus on coordination, while six each address collaboration and communication. These studies explore how AI supports various teamwork functions: in coordination, AI optimizes task allocation, improves effort estimation, and support project management; in collaboration, it enhances pair programming, decision-making, and documentation; and in communication, AI facilitates team meetings and analyzes team sentiment.

Answer to RQ4. To classify AI technologies and their corresponding roles, we adopted the classification presented by Mukhamediev et al. [13], with large language models (LLM) added as an additional category due to recent advancements in the field. Figure 3 shows that natural language processing (NLP) is the most dominant technology, followed by machine learning (ML). The findings suggest an evolution from classic AI techniques, such as NLP and ML algorithms, towards more advanced technologies like LLM. In terms of AI roles, most studies focus on applications with lower levels of autonomy, such as models and tools, while relatively few explore higher autonomy roles like agents, assistants, and bots. This distribution aligns with the AI functions shown in Figure 4, based on the NIST taxonomy of AI use [15]. The most common AI function is recommendation, followed by process automation, detection, and monitoring. These functions primarily operate at the task level and therefore tend to require lower autonomy AI.

Fig. 3: Distribution of Agile teamwork and AI technologies with AI roles.

Fig. 4: Distribution of AI functions.

5 Current Research Gaps in AI and Agile Teamwork

This section presents the key learning points of the study, summarizes the research gaps, and discusses future implications.

Evolution of AI Research in Agile Teamwork. The findings of this study indicate significant growth in research in the integration of AI into Agile teamwork (as shown in Figure 2a). However, the field remains in an exploratory phase, with most studies published in conferences and largely driven by empirical engineering research (as shown in Figure 2b). This shows that there is an active search for practical solution and to determine if the solution is meaningful. A notable gap exists in non-empirical research that consolidates the practical knowledge and explores conceptual models for the integration of AI-driven tools and frameworks designed specifically for Agile practices.

Exploration of AI Technologies. This study finds that NLP is the predominant technology explored in the research (as shown in Figure 3). Despite its

potential to support complex problem-solving, enhance creativity, and assist in decision-making, LLM remains underexplored compared to NLP and ML. More research could examine how LLMs could enhance teamwork in Agile teams. In addition, while the trend of AI technology shifts from classic AI like NLP to more advanced AI like LLM, majority of the use cases continue to involve language-based approaches like tasks allocation, sentiment analysis and requirement analysis. As human aspects in Agile teamwork compose of more than just language, there are promising opportunities to explore further into other modalities of AI, such as images and videos, to enhance team dynamics.

AI Roles in Agile Teamwork. Based on the findings, the distribution of studies in the three aspects of teamwork is relatively equal, with team coordination taking a slightly larger proportion (as shown in Figure 3). In relation to AI roles, majority of the studies on team communication and coordination explore lower autonomy AI while those of team collaboration have a slight focus on higher autonomy roles. The general emphasis on lower autonomy AI roles shows that the research field is in the risk-aware phase. AI which takes on a higher autonomy role would introduce concerns related to trust and control, which is yet to be well understood in Agile teams. Further research could study the impact of higher autonomy AI on team interactions and how AI might transition from being a mere tool to an autonomous agent that actively supports teamwork.

Threats to Validity. To mitigate potential threats and biases, we adhered to Wohlin et al. [16] guidelines. For *internal validity*, we followed the strategy outlined in Section 3 to define search terms, libraries, and inclusion-exclusion criteria. A key challenge was the lack of explicit use of 3C terminology in teamwork-related research, particularly regarding team coordination. To address this, relevant studies were inferred, and a clear definition of the 3C dimensions was established. Additionally, various digital libraries were used to ensure a comprehensive and inclusive collection of research studies. In cases of ambiguity, both authors collaboratively reviewed the studies to reach a consensus, ensuring consistency in study selection. To minimize bias in data extraction and synthesis regarding *conclusion validity*, both authors independently reviewed and cross-validated the extracted data. Any disagreements were resolved through discussion to ensure the reliability and accuracy of the findings.

6 Conclusion

This study provides a systematic overview of research on the integration of AI into teamwork within Agile software development, focusing on the 3Cs: communication, collaboration, and coordination. The results indicate that the research field is in an early exploratory phase to integrate AI into teamwork. While the existing studies are relatively balanced across the three aspects, language-based technologies—particularly natural language processing—are the most commonly explored. In contrast, large language models remain underexplored. Similarly, most studies focus on AI roles with lower levels of autonomy, such as tools and models, while higher-autonomy roles like agents and assistants have not

been widely examined. These findings present research gaps and opportunities for future work to broaden the scope of AI applications and explore how more advanced, autonomous technologies can support and enhance Agile teamwork.

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